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B I B R A C T E

Visiting the Margins.

INnovative **CUL**tural **TO**urism in European peripheries

Ancient paths to the future

INCULTUM pilot #6, Bibracte – Morvan (FR)

INNOVATION FACTSHEET

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CONTEXT

Ancient paths to the future is implemented in a small part of the Morvan Regional Nature Park (420 km², 3,800 inhabitants in twelve village communities). Morvan (3,000 km²; 52,000 inhabitants) is a **mountainous area located in the centre of France, affected by a very strong population decline (80%) throughout the 20th century. Today, the economy relies on three pillars: cattle breeding, forestry and, increasingly for several decades, the residential economy (sectors of services including tourism and welcoming of new inhabitants).**

The territory is recognised for the quality and the “wilderness” its rural landscape, as well as for its relative proximity to large population centres, such as Paris and Lyon Metropolis. These are the main factors of its touristic and residential attractiveness, which have increased since the COVID 19 crisis.

An emblematic rural path of the pilot project area. Copyright: Bibracte (Antoine Maillier).

However, this landscape is rapidly changing under the triple action of the continuous decline of agricultural activity, unsustainable forestry practices and the already very visible effects of global climate change.

In this context, the pilot project aims to participate in the future of the territory **by organising a well-managed tourism offer that mobilises all local actors**, including the economic sectors that are part of the “landscape making”.

To develop these ambitions, ***Ancient paths to the future* is based on an integrated territorial approach** developed around the heritage site of *Bibracte*, the archaeological site of an ephemeral town from the 1st century BC, doubly protected as a historic monument and a natural landscape. Since the 1990, Bibracte has been a major scientific centre in Europe and a French well renowned cultural and tourist destination. BIBRACTE EPCC is the dedicated public establishment managing the site (see Appendix).

The aim of the project is to take advantage of the well-established number of visitors to Bibracte (around 100,000 per year) **to irrigate the surrounding area by developing a wide-ranging offer improving the quality of services** (accommodation, catering, mobility, etc.) **and by mobilising the maximum number of local stakeholders and inhabitants.**

The following diagram details the components of the project:

- a territory considered as a Common that is generating different reasons for attachment;
- conceptual tools that are used in a logical order and in an iterative way, with each cycle helping to strengthen the approach a little more;
- stakeholders who need to be involved;
- participatory mechanisms developed to build an active heritage and territorial community of stakeholders.

Conceptual diagram of the territorial experimentation project into which the Ancient Paths to the Future pilot project fits. Copyright: Bibracte (Flore Coppin, Vincent Guichard).

The regional project is based on a common territorial element, the landscape, which is expressed in a number of ways, such as the paths, the forest, the water and the tangible and intangible heritage bequeathed by the agro-pastoral society of past centuries.

The landscape approach is the driving force behind the community-building method, because of its ability to mobilise people and the holistic approach to the area that it enables.

The stakeholders involved in the project are organised into thematic consultation and project groups.

In this factsheet we propose to explore the main innovations developed in the framework of Ancient paths to the future:

1. The cultivation of the attachment of the inhabitants for heritage and landscape as a vector for social cohesion and action;
2. The activation of levers to activate and stimulate the heritage community;
3. The safeguarding of the coherence and sustainability of the territorial project through an integrated approach using territorial entrepreneurship and territorial intelligence as tools for making different sectors of activity that shape the landscape and the economy working together.

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I. CULTIVATING AN ATTACHEMENT TO THE LANDSCAPE

The attachment of the inhabitants to the territory's heritage and landscape is a vector of social cohesion and action.

Expressing attachment to the landscape

Ancient Paths to the Future assumes that an area can be promoted even more effectively if its inhabitants are aware of its uniqueness and richness. This awareness is a factor in commitment and motivation of the community to maintain the area's heritage features. It fosters a sense of place attachment, collective spatial identity and pride.

To achieve this, the managing partners of the protected area of Bibracte – Morvan des Sommets use the “landscape approach” as developed as part of the Grand Site de France policy.

Bibracte has been involved in the **Grand Site de France approach** since 2007 (see appendix). In 2022, the label has been renewed for the second time with an extended territory and a more ambitious action programme. The definition of the perimeter of the new project territory and the main lines of action have been co-designed through cycles of surveys involving inhabitants and local elected representatives. In this manner, **Landscape and Heritage field workshops** have been organised with each village community where elected officials and inhabitants were invited to identify the sites they found most interesting in their environment. After each session, meetings were organised in town councils where participants were invited to reposition the route they have walked on the oldest available cadastral maps of the region dating from the first half of the 19th century.

Landscape and Heritage field workshop around the village of Glux-en-Glenne.
Copyright: Bibracte.

These surveys revealed **the strong attachment of the inhabitants to the very dense network of paths and trackways which structures the territory and constitutes its singularity**. This attachment had not been foreseen by the organizers. It is now serving as a lever for building an active heritage community that includes the twelve village communities of the Grand Site de France.

Rural paths, a Common to be reactivated

As the plans and cadastral registers clearly show, **the majority of the paths are owned by the village communities**. This network is **particularly dense** on the territory, due to two combined factors: the great dispersion of the habitat since the Middle Ages and the absence of agricultural reorganisation during the second half of the 20th century. The inventory showed that the network amounted to 1,100 km for a surface area of 420 km², i.e. a density of 2.6 km of paths per km². This heritage is all the more important because, in this region, village communities rarely own other communal land.

Many of these paths are now abandoned and overgrown, but even in this case their course is still visible in the form of ground movements and the remains of dry-stone walls or old hedges. For the others, maintenance is justified by different, sometimes antagonistic, uses: access to houses or agricultural plots, logging, recreational or sporting use (hunting, hiking, etc.).

In our case, **the reactivation of this common heritage requires a collective awareness of this shared resource – which is in the process of being achieved – and then the implementation of management rules and the sustainable mobilisation of resources to ensure its preservation.**

OLD MAPS, A FANTASTIC TOOL FOR BUILDING A SHARED REPRESENTATION OF THE TERRITORY

The physiognomy of a territory never ceases to change in line with the evolution of the socio-economic context, just as the sociology of the population never ceases to be recomposed. In this respect, the changes that have occurred in Morvan over the last two centuries are considerable. The agricultural "golden age" of the 19th century resulted in a very open landscape that was truly gardened by its inhabitants. This landscape was then progressively abandoned in favour of the forest, which size doubled during the 20th century, while **the emergence of the residential economy** in the second half of the 20th century saw the arrival of a new population lacking the long memory of peasant families. In this context, the first cadastral plans, known as "Napoleonic" because the emperor Napoleon Bonaparte was the initiator, but which were drawn up until the middle of the 19th century, proved to be a choice material for constructing a shared representation of the territory, all the more so because they are easily accessible as a copy is always kept in the town halls. These plans give a very precise picture of the organisation of the territory at the time of the agricultural maximum. In particular, they show the boundaries of the former agricultural plots reclaimed by the forest, the location of the vanished hamlets and, above all, the pattern of the very dense network of paths, only a small part of which is still active at the beginning of the

1839 cadastral map of Glux-en-Glenne (detail)

1/ Mapping of the trackways in the commune of Glux-en-Glenne following the participatory inventory carried out in the commune in 2020 // 2/ Inventory of trackways be regularised. Source: Taloua Colas, Master 2 thesis, Geography, Planning, Environment, Development, University of Nantes, 2020.

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A shared management plan for the network of rural paths

Only some of the rural paths (about 300 km, i.e. a third of the network) are currently subject to formalised management measures, with dedicated resources provided either by village communities, or by groups of village communities: those included in the district walking plans (PDIPR). For the others, **maintenance is left to the initiative of the users** (inhabitants, farmers, foresters, hunters, sports organisations, etc.) according to their needs.

Following a survey conducted at the end of 2022 by the Grand Site de France team on the territory, the village communities clearly expressed their desire **to engage in a shared approach of the management of the paths network**.

Heritage inventory session with residents end of 2021
Copyright: Bibracte

The first stage of the work, which is still in progress, consists of **establishing a mapped inventory**. Using cadastral maps and other available cartographic documents, the project aims to establish **an atlas of the territory's rural paths**, including a complete and precise cartography of the paths and to describe each section with descriptive data (physical condition of the path, existing uses, landscape interest) and indications on its management (registration on the PDIPR, marking, maintenance methods). The inventory is led by the Rural Paths referents that we have been appointed within the municipal councils and by the members of the Rural Paths working group that federates the Rural paths referents of the project territory. **The Grand Site de France team coordinates the working group and provides a method and technical advice.**

In practice, we have programmed an inventory method of the **open source software QFIELD** so that villagers can use the app on a tablet and enter data during their field walks. These data are then grouped together on a public **webSIG** administered by the Morvan Regional Nature Park (see box below).

During the summer of 2022, a **“General Assembly on rural paths”** brought together most of the parties involved in their management – villages, groups of village communities, districts (Départements), tourist offices, the French hiking federation, etc. – and reiterated the particularly complex regulatory and administrative framework for their management.

Following consultation at the end of 2022, the village communities then embarked on a shared approach to path management. One of the aims of this approach is to produce a rural path management plan in the short term, which could take the form of a charter.

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RECOGNIZING LANDSCAPE AS A COMMON GOOD

Commons are shared resources, managed and maintained collectively by a community.

The community establishes **rules** to preserve and sustain these resources while providing its members with the opportunity and right to use them, or, if the community decides, granting this right to all. These resources can be natural (a forest, a river), material (a tool, a house, a power plant) or immaterial (knowledge, software) (*Wikipedia France*). As a shared resource, a cultural or natural heritage asset is a common property in its own right, provided that it benefits from the **attachment of a community**, which in this case is referred to as a heritage community, and that this community is active, in the sense that it respects the rules it has defined to ensure the preservation of the asset.

Therefore, a network of paths or irrigation canals shared and managed by a community are typical examples of **territorial commons**. In the sense of the **European Landscape Convention**, a landscape (as "an area, as perceived by people, whose character is the result of the action and interaction of natural and/or human factors") can also be considered as a **common good** when it arouses the attachment of a community and when the latter provides itself with the means to manage it with the appropriate rules. In this respect, the joint creation of a network of paths that criss-cross the landscape is a step towards the **joint creation of the landscape as a whole**.

A DIGITAL TOOL FOR INVENTORING THE RURAL PATHS HERITAGE

Cadastrés, existing maps, but also the use of geomatics and geographic information systems are necessary to establish a **reliable database** allowing a better management of these paths and a sharing of the knowledge of this common heritage.

University work made it possible to develop and validate **an inventory and characterisation protocol** in 2020, up to the creation of an **embedded GIS project** on a tablet via the **QFIELD application** built with all the data (scan25, orthophotos, land registry, departmental and communal roads, rural paths), in order to characterise the rural paths in the field and record their condition.

A **GPS plot** is generated for each route in order to accommodate the attribute data entered in the field and to highlight the actual passage of the path in the field.

Inhabitants and elected representatives of the 12 village communities of the Grand Site de France have been trained in using this tool and have been working since 2021 **to survey the paths** of the territory by qualifying them on a dedicated application. For those who are reluctant to use the computer tool, it is also possible to note their observations on a **printed map**, the information being entered later on the GIS.

The online map of the rural paths of the Grand Site de France viewer (ternum-bfc.fr)

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Supporting the emergence of the heritage community

In addition, as part of the coordination of the heritage community, the Morvan Regional Nature Park has been organising **artistic residencies** for the past three years, with the publication of a **collection of illustrated booklets**, the *Carnets d'arpentage [Survey Booklets] du Grand Site de France*.

Walking the paths with the **elected representatives and the inhabitants** allows the three artists in residence (landscape designers and illustrators) to **observe and collect their perceptions of the territory's landscapes, and to gather local stories** in order to translate the participants' feelings into illustrations and writing. These notebooks evoke in a poetic and sensitive way the spaces and landscapes travelled, experienced, loved, looked at and admired by the inhabitants of the territory. They express the common reasons for the inhabitants' attachment to their territory and its rural paths. **They thus contribute to strengthening the attachment of the inhabitants to the territory of the Grand Site de France.** Produced in small runs using a traditional silk-screen printing process, but also available for consultation on the Grand Site de France website, these notebooks make a major contribution to strengthening the attachment of local residents. They also help to produce original images that are a favourite material for the area's communication tools.

An illustrated booklet of the Grand Site de France Bibracte - Morvan des Sommets, downloaded online: <https://www.bibracte.fr/un-grand-site-de-france>

II. ACTIVATING AND STIMULATING THE HERITAGE COMMUNITY

Ancient paths to the Future is supporting the constitution of an active heritage community around a common good: the rural paths.

Organize the heritage community

As part of the Grand Site de France initiative, the activation of **the landscape community** is based on working groups formed around the different components and issues of the landscape. These groups are led by members of the management team, supported as far as possible by scientists, experts and cultural players involved in the territorial project.

The Rural Paths group brings together around thirty people (elected representatives, volunteer residents and local professionals). Its main objectives are:

- To draw up an inventory of the network of footpaths and their uses;
- To prepare a shared management plan based on priority uses;
- In the area of recreational and sporting uses, to identify routes, enhance them (by restoring them and marking them out), organise the services required by users (access, accommodation, catering) and promote them (publication of maps);
- To work in synergy with other working groups where necessary.

The Rural Paths group is led by the GSF's Heritage and Tourism Officer, who is also the APF project coordinator. Her role is to help set and achieve concrete short-term objectives, which is essential to ensure the long-term commitment of the group's members. This involves drawing up the inventory (atlas), putting in place tools and working methods (field survey, maps, etc), organising field trips and participative workcamps, and devising and implementing an enhancement strategy.

The assessment of the current situation and the preparation of the management plan will primarily involve elected representatives and members of the public who are members of the working group,

Mapping of the territory's atlas of walks with the rural paths working group in January 2022. Copyright: Bibracte

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while the strengthening of recreational and sporting activities will also involve tourism and service providers, particularly those who are members of the Tourism group.

Enhancing the value of the path network for local residents and stakeholders

Different approaches are being used to enhance the value of the network of paths and strengthen the attachment of residents to it. In 2022 and 2023, **volunteer summer heritage work camps** were organised in partnership with the national NGO Rempart Federation, which brings together nearly two hundred associations that organise heritage restoration work camps open to volunteers, and the regional NGO Tremplin - Hommes et Patrimoine, which uses heritage restoration as a means of socio-economic reintegration. The dozen or so volunteers were able to take part in the restoration of an abandoned path and its dry-stone boundary walls, and to learn about the Grand Site de France approach and the regional project developed within this framework, thanks to contributions from experts (archaeologist, restorer, landscape architect, etc.). This original offer has attracted architecture, archaeology, landscape, and art history students who are sensitive to environmental issues. As a result of the work carried out, a section of the path has been restored and is now part of a new discovery trail on the slopes of Mont Beuvray. At the end of this experiment, **the aim is to make this training course a permanent feature in the form of a summer school**, during which students will come and learn about the working method used in the Bibracte – Morvan des Sommets ecological transition laboratory, while also getting their “hands dirty”.

A summer heritage workcamp organised in July 2022, in partnership with the NGO Rempart and co-financed by INCULTUM. Copyright: Bibracte (Antoine Maillier).

Walking along the paths allows us to discover the rich heritage of the territory and, at the same time, **helps to create links between walkers**. For this reason, in the frame of the pilot project, we have organised a programme of cultural walks with the aim of **mobilising local inhabitants with very different profiles** and who have little opportunity to talk to each other. As far as possible, these walks highlight **local inhabitants** (a farmer who maintains his hedges in an exemplary way, a water mill owner who has restored it, etc.) and they also involve "**experts**" (such as scientists invited to explain the geology of the area, its hydrology, its biodiversity, environmental and forest management technicians, etc.) **and artists** who are invited to "**shift the focus**" of the participants and facilitate dialogue between them.

In 2022, 6 cultural walks have been organised in 7 of the 12 villages of the territory, mobilising more than 400 participants: inhabitants, visitors and members of the heritage community (and often reaching the maximum of 50 participants that we have set for these events in order to preserve the quality of the exchanges).

Through these actions, the paths regain their function as spaces of sociability and they tend to become "**third places**", understood as "*spaces in which the will of a community of citizens to move towards a better world is embodied, whose network redraws with common sense, cooperation and solidarity the territory in which they are anchored, and position themselves at the heart of exchanges between public actors, private actors and citizens*" (Wikipedia France, adapted).

Regarding these actions carried out along the paths, we can still speak of a "**Political Art workshop**". **In the thinking of the sociologist and philosopher Bruno Latour, Political Art** consists of the simultaneous use of scientific methods and artistic practices to analyse societal issues and to enrich the political decision-making process.

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Taking a step back and learning from the experience of others

Organised on an annual basis, the conference Entretiens de Bibracte-Morvan were initially intended to discuss the issues facing the region in the light of scientific opinion. Open to all, in recent years they have explored the concepts of the Commons, climate change, solidarity between humans and non-humans and agro ecology. The concepts were explored in practical terms through sessions organised in the field, in close contact with local players and, for the most recent editions, with the involvement of artists.

In 2023, the 17th Entretiens, organised as part of the INCULTUM pilot project, looked at the concept of heritage and the role of the arts and cultural action in fostering local people's attachment to their area. Over 150 participants took part in the series of lectures, walks and meetings, sharing experiences and engaging debates.

III. THE TOURISM PROJECT AS A LEVER FOR THE REGIONAL PROJECT

In order to ensure the coherence and sustainability of the tourism project, the pilot project adopts an integrated approach mobilising the concept of territorial entrepreneurship and embracing the different sectors of activity that shape the landscape and the economy.

A federative initiative: the Tour du Morvan des Sommets

The **Tour du Morvan des Sommets** is a new cultural itinerary for discovering the region and the flagship project developed as part of INCULTUM. It responds to a desire shared by the elected representatives of the twelve village communities and its implementation makes a major contribution to the desire to work together on a regional scale.

Workshops held by the Rural paths group to design the route led to the definition of an itinerary that has been improved with the support of local walking associations and technicians from the Morvan Regional Natural Park.

The Tour is a 140 km long hiking tour that links the twelve villages, making the best possible use of the network of paths. By linking the twelve village communities, the itinerary invites visitors to discover a rich and living heritage that expresses the ways in which people have lived here, past and present. It aims **to become a tool for raising visitors' awareness of climate change and a showroom for traditional practices and know-how that can inspire solutions for sustainable land management.**

The route was tested in 2022 by a tourism professional, who validated its interest and feasibility. It was put into service in summer 2023, with the support of temporary promotional material pending its homologation as a national hiking route.

Sectoral working groups on the common landscape

The new discovery route now **is the meeting point for the local multi-sectorial entrepreneurship projects** and serves as a catalyst for landscape initiatives.

In addition to the Rural Paths group mentioned above, the Grand Site de France initiative gathers four other thematic groups. Even if the Grand Site de France management team does not have economic competence, it nevertheless has **a legitimate role as a facilitator of the territorial project and as a catalyst.** As such, **the development of territorial entrepreneurship** is an integral part of the territorial approach. It can **contribute both to the sustainable socio-economic development of the territory and to the maintenance of its landscape quality and heritage.**

Its collegial governance encourages cooperation between all the players, and the emergence of territorial dynamics based on the territory's resources, its landscape, natural and built heritage and its intangible values. **The team coordinates and facilitates territorial entrepreneurship projects.** The responsibility for planning, financing and managing the projects is left to the local actors and legitimate local authorities.

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Within the framework of the pilot project, the socio-economic actors of the territory find in the approach a space of shared values facilitating the emerging dynamics and the entrepreneurship of the territory.

The Tourism group brings together around twenty local players (tourist offices and tourism service providers) who are working to build a “slow tourism” offer throughout the four seasons, combining leisure activities and outdoor sports, heritage and cultural discovery and encounters with local people, particularly along the Tour du Morvan des Sommets.

The Art & Territory group brings together around twenty local artists to develop collective projects.

The Agriculture group was set up to forge links between long-established farmers, all of whom raise cattle, and new farmers, who are often developing diversified projects geared towards short distribution channels. To this end, it has the support of the Grand Site de France project manager, who is seconded on a part-time basis by a local chamber of agriculture. The priorities are to facilitate the takeover of farms, create links with the local economy (farm visits, farm to fork offers) and strengthen solidarity within the farmers community. The group is now an association set up in 2023 with around ten members and it has been accredited as a Groupement d'intérêt économique et Environnemental (GIEE), a Ministry of Agriculture label designed to promote the local organisation of players in the agricultural sector around sustainable collective projects. The next step is to implement concrete projects, such as the creation of a reception area or the development of a catering offer available in the form of buffets.

The Forest group is a part of the forest experimentation laboratory set up in 2021. Led by Bibracte's Forest Project Manager, this group is being set up at the time of writing with the aim of establishing a dialogue on forest management, at a time when it is the subject of very lively debate in the Morvan, because industrial logging methods are damaging the landscape in a way that is less and less accepted by the local population.

Another example is the participatory approach launched in autumn 2023 on the subject of water, designed both to better characterise this resource, which is subject to shortages in the summer months, and to make it a component of the local community by relying on an original system of shared management of springs, the Associations syndicales libres, which is widely developed locally. Here again, the creation of a dedicated working group is a means of action that we aim to deploy.

Finally, the theme of professional integration has been developed over the last two decades to help enhance the Bibracte – Mont-Beuvray heritage site (restoration of archaeological remains, forestry maintenance). It is now being mobilised in support of the Grand Site de France initiative, for example to maintain the network of paths.

The region's tourism observatory

The development of the tourist economy is a real lever for the sustainable development of the region. However, this development potential comes up against widespread mistrust among the local population, who fear that their living environment is being “touristified” in an uncontrolled way, as other areas are suffering.

In response to this mistrust, a system designed to create a form of territorial tourism intelligence has been in place at Bibracte since 2019. Based on the **EVALTO method** (Fabry et al., 2012), the aim is to overcome preconceived ideas and objectify knowledge of tourism activity by means of in-depth surveys produced and analysed with local residents and stakeholders. In fact, the first edition of the survey showed that both local decision-makers and local residents had a very distorted perception of tourism, particularly as regards holiday tourism, which is much more developed than they think. A new edition of the survey will include hiking and green tourism around Bibracte, in order to provide a more complete picture of the profile and practices of visitors to the area.

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Ancient paths to the future at a glance

Main objectives and results:

Building awareness of the cultural heritage of 1100+ km network of paths:

- Creation of participatory inventory, digital management tool and online map
- Creation of different means of representation of this cultural heritage: sensitive discovery map of the area, survey books

Activation of a heritage community around the heritage of the pathways:

- Creation of different sectorial working groups: agriculture, tourism, rural paths....
- Co-creation of participatory methods to work with the heritage: volunteer landscape and heritage workcamps, cultural walks...

An integrated approach to territorial entrepreneurship:

- Creation of a new flagship cultural route, the Tour du Morvan des Sommets
- Promotion of the destination and the new routes: production of tourism packages, a brochure and of a website dedicated to the new tourist destination
- The Agriculture WP is now an association accredited as a Groupement d'intérêt économique et Environnemental (GIEE), a Ministry of Agriculture label

Main outcomes:

- The Tour du Morvan des Sommets serves as a catalyst for landscape initiatives and is a means of federating economic activities
- Boosted attractiveness of the territory through new narratives strengthening local identity and attracting new visitors
- Project of homologation of the new cultural route by the French national hiking federation for increased visibility and notoriety
- Development of a new destination website to promote narratives of the ecological transition and local involvement in tourism
- The GSF landscape maintenance actions showcase local sustainability practices and know-how and it works towards to strengthening the inhabitants' attachment to shared values and to raise the awareness of the challenges of climate change

Contact:

Project officer: Flore Coppin, flore.coppin@bibracte.fr
www.bibracte.fr
www.grandsite-bibracte-morvan.fr

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ANNEXES

THE GRANDS SITES DE FRANCE AND THE PUBLIC ESTABLISHMENTS OF CULTURAL COOPERATION (ETABLISSEMENTS PUBLICS DE COOPERATION CULTURELLE), TWO INNOVATIVE MECHANISMS FOR TERRITORIAL PUBLIC ACTION

The Grand Site de France approach: an experimental policy at the service of rural territories

The Grand Site de France approach originates from the State's concern, expressed at the end of the 1970s, to combat the harmful effects of excessive tourist numbers on the most emblematic protected sites in France. After focusing on curative measures (development of car parks, installation of services, etc.) within the framework of "Grand Site operations (OGS)", a second stage in this policy was reached in 2001 with the introduction of the Grand Site de France label. Issued by the ministry in charge of landscape policy and reviewed every six years, this is a demanding label that is intended to encourage local authorities to take responsibility for the sustainable management of their most emblematic sites, well beyond just tourism issues. It is awarded to an average of one site per year. Another particularity of this policy is its non-normative character: the methods of defining the geographical perimeter of the label, of mobilising the stakeholders and of organising the governance of the labelled sites are left to the discretion of the candidates. In this sense, the Grand Site de France approach is a real laboratory for innovation in the management of rural territories. It is based on the hypothesis that the landscape approach (*la démarche paysagère*) is an effective and virtuous lever for territorial action, due to its capacity to mobilise players and its ability to encourage a holistic and integrated approach to the territorial project. Around fifty territories are involved in the approach; they are federated within an independent organisation, the *Réseau des Grands Sites de France*, which has become over the years a think tank in terms of public policies based on the landscape approach and which shares its experience internationally within an international training and exchange centre.

[Réseau des Grands Sites de France - Home-en \(grandsitedefrance.com\) // www.polepatrimoine.org](http://www.polepatrimoine.org)

Public establishments for cultural cooperation, an original tool for the shared management of heritage spaces and cultural services

Public establishments for cultural cooperation (EPCC) were introduced in France in 2002 by law. This is a new type of public establishment whose originality lies in the joint desire of public bodies (local authorities, the State/Ministry of Culture, national public establishments) to pool their resources to better manage a heritage space or a cultural service of regional or national importance. The founding members participate in the EPCC's board of directors, which is the decision-making body for the validation of the establishment's project and budget. This system commits the EPCC's partners over the long term, which encourages the implementation of long-term management plans. There are several hundred EPCCs, active in the most diverse sectors of culture. The recent extension of their field of action to the management of environmental services is proof of the success of the formula and broadens their field of action.